

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

SALINIZATION OF SOILS IN THE SHIRVAN PLAIN AND ITS IMPACT ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTIVITY

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Abstract

The article provides information about research conducted on the Shirvan plain lands. The studies have shown that the soil of the plain is salinized to varying degrees. As a result, the productivity of agricultural crops has relatively decreased depending on the salt content in the soil. Certain agro-meliorative measures should be implemented to maintain the reclamation status of these lands and to improve their fertility.

Keywords: climate, salinization, fertility, ecological condition, productivity

Introduction: In Azerbaijan, the production of agricultural crops mainly takes place on irrigated lands. The increase in the world population, the reduction of arable land, water scarcity, the deterioration of ecological conditions, and climate variability all negatively affect the development of agriculture. One of the most pressing global issues of the modern era is ensuring food supply for the population. Due to its favorable physical and geographical conditions, the country has a rich climate that provides a foundation for agricultural development. The Shirvan plain, located in the Kura-Araz lowland, also possesses favorable natural conditions, although its soils are salinized to varying degrees. At present, studying the extent of soil salinization in the plain and the productivity of agricultural crops is considered an important issue.

Research Object and Methodology. The research focused on the soils of the Shirvan plain. To determine the current condition of the irrigated soils of the plain, previous studies conducted in this area were thoroughly and comparatively examined. Research carried out in different years on the soils of the Ucar and Kurdamir districts, located within the plain, was clarified and comparatively analyzed with the present situation.

Analysis and Discussion

In the modern era, climate change, one of the global changes, has primarily affected agriculture, resulting in reduced crop yields. The Kura-Araz lowland, which is the main agricultural zone of the country, also has favorable climatic conditions. The soils of the Shirvan plain, located within this lowland, are suitable for agriculture and possess significant potential. However, as in other regions of the country, improper irrigation in this area has led to a decline in soil fertility. According to geological data, most of the sediments in the mountains surrounding the Shirvan plain from the north are salinized with various salts. The salinization of the plain's soils is also influenced by mud volcanoes in the piedmont zone and the alluvial sediments flowing from them. Additionally, saline groundwater contributes to the salinization of the plain's soils. It should be noted that groundwater is found at different depths in different parts of the plain. In some areas, it is located at a depth of 10 meters or more, while in others it ranges from 5 to 10 meters, and in some places, it lies at even shallower depths. The soils of the plain mainly belong

to the gray-brown soil type, with chestnut soils present in the piedmont areas. The parent rocks forming the gray-brown soils are of alluvial origin and are characterized by salinity. These soils are distinguished by high carbonate content [6]. Overall, the degree of salinization of the Shirvan plain's soils varies greatly. Areas in the piedmont zone of the plain have slightly salinized soils, with salt content in the top meter not exceeding 0.1%. The salinization process is more pronounced in the middle parts of the river alluvial cones, where the salt content in some areas can reach 2–3% in the soil layer. At the same time, the Shirvan plain contains both salinized and non-salinized soils. These non-salinized soils are found in the piedmont zone, covering the Qarameyrem plateau, Padar tire, the upper parts of river alluvial cones, and other areas. Weakly salinized soils are also present in the plain. Based on their chemical composition, the soils of the Shirvan plain are classified into the following types: carbonate-salinized, sulfate-salinized, chloride-salinized, and soils salinized with mixed salts. These soil types are distributed in a scattered manner[1].

Over the years, a number of researchers have conducted studies in the Shirvan plain. V.R. Volobuyev, N.A. Dimo, S.I. Tyuremnov, V.A. Priklnski, M.E. Salayev, M.P. Babayev, G.Sh. Mammadov, Q.Z. Azizov, L.Z. Jalilova, and others have investigated various aspects of the area. V.A. Priklnski noted that the alluvial cones in the western part of the Shirvan plain are nourished by groundwater from rivers. A.A. Grosheym studied the vegetation of the plain in detail and showed that, depending on the types of soils present in the zone, the vegetation undergoes various changes. As soil salinity increases, the vegetation weakens and is gradually replaced by salt-tolerant plants. Primarily, three types of plants are widespread: wormwood, saline grasses, and meadow grasses.

Soil studies in the Shirvan plain were first conducted by S.I. Tyuremnov, who classified the area's soils as belonging to the gray soil group. Later, V.R. Volobuyev, M.E. Salayev, M.P. Babayev, and G.Sh. Məmmədov, in their research, showed that the irrigated gray-meadow and meadow-gray soils of the Shirvan plain entirely cover the alluvial and proluvial plains. The soils of the plain have a heavy granulometric composition and exhibit very low water permeability [5.7].

The granulometric composition of soil significantly affects its water-physical and physical-mechanical properties, air and thermal characteristics, redox conditions, absorption capacity, and the accumulation of humus, total organic matter, and nitrogen. Depending on the granulometric composition, cultivation conditions, timing of field operations, fertilizer application rates, and the placement of agricultural crops vary [6]. In these soils, the proportion of physical clay (≤ 0.01 mm) ranges from 65% to 90%. The heaviest granulometric composition (< 0.001 mm = 36–40%; < 0.018 mm = 80–90%) is observed in irrigated gray-meadow and meadow-gray soils that have been cultivated for long periods. Research conducted in the Ucar Dayag area of the Ucar district in the Shirvan plain has shown that the soils there have a heavy granulometric composition, making this area typical for the Shirvan plain. Soil studies in this area indicated that, along the soil profile, the salt content decreases toward the lower layers. The maximum concentration of salts is observed below the 0–25 cm layer. These soils vary in salinization, ranging from non-salinized to weakly, moderately, and severely salinized. According to the type of salts, the soils are classified as sulfate and chloride-sulfate, and they are calcareous throughout the profile. The CaCO_3 content is 13–15% in irrigated soils and 10–14% in salinized soils. The high carbonate content is attributed to the proximity of groundwater to the surface. During these studies, the relationship between soil salinity and crop yields was also examined. It was found that in areas with high soil salinity, the productivity of crops such as cereals and cotton was reduced [3].

Studies conducted in the Kurdamir district of the Shirvan plain indicate that areas with moderate, severe salinization, and saline soils account for approximately 7.2% of the non-salinized and weakly salinized soils. These soils are heavy in terms of granulometric composition and are calcareous throughout the profile. In soils used for cereal cultivation, the salt content ranges from 0.10% to 0.58%. The results showed that the salts in the soil belong to the sulfate and chloride-sulfate types. The yield of cereals grown on these soils was 29–30 centners per hectare. Overall, the studies indicate that the depth and mineralization of groundwater significantly affect the productivity of agricultural crops [2,4].

It should be noted that recent ecological changes have negatively affected the reclamation status of soils,

accelerating their degradation processes. Therefore, maintaining the reclamation status and fertility of soils remains a critical issue. However, studies conducted in recent years have shown that the hydrogeological and reclamation conditions of the country's irrigated soils have significantly improved, which is the result of the implementation of targeted reclamation measures [4].

Conclusion

Studies have shown that the soils of the Shirvan plain, located in the Kura-Araz lowland, have a heavy granulometric composition and are salinized to varying degrees. Research conducted in the Ucar and Kurdamir districts of the plain has demonstrated that in areas with higher salt content, the productivity of agricultural crops is reduced. To maintain the reclamation status and fertility of these soils, agro-meliorative measures should be implemented.

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